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Research Article

**THE EFFECT OF CSR ON ORGANIZATIONAL
COMMITMENT WITH MODERATING ROLE OF EMOTIONAL
INTELLIGENCE; EVIDENCE FORM PHARMACEUTICAL
COMPANIES**¹Tiwa Park¹Professor, Communication Arts, Bangkok University, Bangkok
tsp.tiwa@gmail.com**Abstract:**

The concept of corporate social responsibility is emerging in every country therefore this study focused on the role of CSR on organizational commitment with moderating role of emotional intelligence. The data was collected from 127 employees working in pharmaceutical companies of Thailand, Bangkok. AMOS was used to find the results and it is revealed that there is positive and significant relationship between CSR and organizational commitment although there is significant moderating effect of emotional intelligence among relationship among CSR and organizational commitment. Moreover this study only focused on affective commitment which is important element and mostly studied.

Keywords: *Pharmaceutical Companies; Emotional Intelligence; CSR; Organizational Commitment***Corresponding author:****Tiwa Park,**Professor, Communication Arts, Bangkok University, Bangkok
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INTRODUCTION:

The concept of CSR arises in late 1800-century after the British industrial revolution. This revolution has changed the entire employment trends and as a result most of the labor shifted from agricultural sector to industrial sector. At that time the working environment of these industries was not remarkable and it was dangerous, without any health & safety measures. Child labor was also common. Till the end of 18th century there were considerable voices to make the businesses socially responsible (1). Though the idea of CSR is emerging form 18th century but it was adopted as organizational strategy in 1950s. The concept of CSR has been investigated from different perspectives such as normative, political, stakeholder and institutional perspectives; all these perspectives are considered as great contribution to the knowledge of CSR (2). Generally, the fundamental motivation behind every business is to achieve maximum level of profitability by providing goods and services to the customer. The theory “the invisible hands” by Adam Smith in 1776, explained that the combine conduct of individuals serves general public much better than any planned or organized effort from social planners (3). According to (4), quoted by (5) as “father of CSR”, guaranteed that CSR would keep on guiding organizations in future times. (6) agreed with Bowen when they reminded that currently, CSR has gained significant consideration.

There are various definitions of CSR in past studies but according to (7; 8; 9; 10), there is yet no common definition. Initially, (11) defines CSR as an activity just not for profitability; it exists and works beyond financial and industrial benefits. (12) explained that CSR is not only financial or legal responsibility of country but actually its responsibility towards society. (13) argued that CSR should be a voluntary activity rather than an obligation. (14) has introduced four categories of CSR, economic responsibilities (profitable), legal responsibilities (obeying the regulations), ethical responsibilities (being ethical) and philanthropic responsibilities (good citizen).

The researchers like (15; 16), emphasized to explore relationship between CSR and organizational commitments, but CSR in Asian developing countries is still obscure and under-research. In addition, worker’s self-assessment of CSR activities has been ignored or missing. Therefore, it is useful to consider employees’ self-assessment of CSR. It is seen that the manufacturing firms which are associated with the discharge of dangerous squanders into the environment, have more pressure and focus on such activities can enhance their corporate image in society. Conversely, non-manufacturing firms may have less pressure for CSR activities as these make

less social dangers comparative to manufacturing firms (17). Taking everything into account, CSR exercises are critical for both employees and society. Firms which take part in CSR activities keep in mind their end goal which is to get a good corporate image in the public arena and employee retention. These organizations think about workers as their internal customers and also consider their commitment and motivation as source of success (2). Consequently, main purpose of this study is to investigate the employees' perspective of CSR and its effect on Organizational Commitment (OC) among employees associated with supply chain process.

The term organizational commitment acquired from the book of (18) which was published thirty years ago named as “the Organization Man”, in which they outlined that “The organization man is not only working for the organization, but also belongs to it”. The work of (19) asserted that “There is need of feeling to understand the behaviors and attitudes of others in every hierarchical level, which loyalty belongs to the purpose of organization”. (20) termed organizational commitment as a set of different multiple commitments present in groups including both inside as well as outside the organization. There are many definitions and measurement scales of organizational commitment but exemplary work was done by (21) by defining OC as a psychological state of mind, having three different components, desire, need and obligation. Moreover they explained desire as affective commitment, need as continuance commitment and obligation as normative commitment. Some other researchers have expanded their area of investigation from traditional organizational commitment to personal traits of the employees such as emotional intelligence and their impact on organizational commitment (22; 23). (24) defined affective commitment as the state of emotions being attached, and it’s a bond between organization and employees which includes involvement and identification of an employee as well as satisfaction level being member of the organization (25; 21; 26) and this dimension is mostly being used in organizations and literature. Thus, new studies of (27; 28; 29; 30) have analyzed individual traits like emotional intelligence with the motive to facilitate organizations in formulating HR policies for obtaining maximum desired outcomes from employees. Therefore this study has mainly focused on affective commitment of employees engaged in supply chain processes with the moderating effect of emotional intelligence. Emotional Intelligence is defined by (31) and later on by (32) as “the ability to perceive, understand, and

regulate emotions, is a personal trait that characterizes how an individual's psychological well-being influences their attitudes and behaviors". According to (33), emotional intelligence facilitates organizational relationship with its major stakeholders and has positive relationship with organizational commitment.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

In today's era the major discussion is in on the subject that whether organizations should bear a more prominent social obligation. Moreover, it is broadly discussed that there is an across the board support for the idea of Corporate Social Responsibility (34). As indicated by the idea of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), an organization should focus on societal and ecological outcomes of their activities rather than traditional objective of efficiency and profitability. In the present period, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has gained much consideration from organizations and considered as a high-profile business strategy. Business firms are utilizing CSR as a tool for marketing their products and also to achieve consumer's satisfaction. This relationship of consumer satisfaction is explored in numerous studies (35; 36). However, there are also some studies which explored relationship between CSR and its effectiveness from employees' perspective (37; 38). A worldwide survey of 1122 chief executive officers, records the advantages of CSR because of its attractiveness for current and potential employees (39).

CSR & Employees

There are different theories and viewpoints regarding CSR and employees. According to (40), the worth and autonomy of the employees are the guiding forces for companies. Profitable companies give preference to the employee's individual interest rather than their interest in company. (41) argued that basic activity like obeying the law is not corporate social responsibility, in fact it comprises the activities which are taken to enhance the trust, loyalty and motivation in employees. Regarding CSR and employees, (42) studied that both existing and potential employees have some beliefs about the company like fair wage, good career and skills development opportunity along with good working environment. (43) stated that social responsibilities of the company include treatment, involvement in decision making process, good working environment, provision of job security and also leisure facilities. Moreover, they discussed the top management actions which are deriving factors for loyal, satisfied and committed employees having role in signifying the company's future value. (44) stated employees as

a source of competitive advantage. Companies usually make their long-term planning keeping in view the competence level of their employees. In return employees expect fulfillment of their financial, social and emotional needs. According to (45), ergonomics deals with physical working environment like good sitting arrangement, lights, air and ventilation. (45) and (46), also agree that good physical working environment determine the productivity and well-being of the employees.

Organizational Commitment

(21) define the organizational commitment (OC) as "Organizational commitment (OC) is an individual's psychological attachment to the organization." As far as the relationship between CSR and OC is concerned, the study of (47), analyzed the positive relationship between perceived employee's CSR and organizational commitment. In relationship between CSR and organizational outcomes, there is significant role of employees (48; 49). (16; 50) explored positive relationship between affective OC, CSR. Moreover their studies argued that employee as an internal stakeholder has a prominent impact of CSR strategy development and implementation. The management motivational quotations like "*doing well by doing good*" and "*what is good for society is good for the company*" encouraged the researchers to investigate the relationship between CSR and organizational outcome (47). The organizational support theory explains that affective OC is defined by organizational CSR activities towards employees (38). Most of the studies to explore relationship between CSR and OC, have relied upon "social identity theory" which has argued that the socially responsible companies ensure employee's social identity resulting in positive effect on OC (16; 50). Like CSR, internal marketing has positive and significant relationship between organizational commitment (65).

Emotional Intelligence (EI)

(31; 32; 51), has defined the emotional intelligence as "the ability to perceive, understand, and regulate emotions, is a personal trait that characterizes how an individual's psychological well-being influences their attitudes and behaviors". EI is considered as intangible employee's characteristic that can affect the organizational performance. Numerous studies found significant and positive relationship among organizational commitment and emotional intelligence (33). (29) found positive relationship between EI, OC and job satisfaction. (52), investigated relationship between emotional intelligence and demographics components of

employees like, age, sex, marital status, education and work experience. They found that emotional intelligence can be increased by proper on the job trainings. (53) explained that the emotional intelligence plays important role in organizational growth. Emotional intelligence enables the employees to evaluate their actions and thinking process. According to the study of (54), emotional intelligence strengthens the employee's career adoptability.

Research Gap

Significant research work has been done regarding relationship between CSR and organizational commitment. (38) have studied the relationship between CSR and OC. Existing literature on CSR reveals that this concept is significantly recognized in whole world (55; 56). However, there are some socio-economical factors which have highlighted the divergence in understanding the concept of CSR and hence it varies from country to country. Hence, the impact of culture factor is significant to understand the concept of CSR. (57; 58; 59), compared the difference of CSR activities among different countries. Most of the studies are conducted in context of western countries like Europe and America. However, recent developments in Asian countries originated the need of CSR studies. (56) discussed that CSR is still not widely explored and there is significant shortage of research especially in developing Asian countries. (60) studied CSR as administrative technique to manage employees in India. (6) explored CSR's consequences for employees in Korea. (61) investigate relationship between CSR and firm performance. (62) studied the "Impact of CSR on Job Attitudes, Job Satisfaction and OC". (49) investigated the impact of CSR on OC with mediating effect of work significance and perceived organizational support. (52) also investigated "CSR and employee engagement with moderating role of autonomy and individualism". (63) studied "CSR in developing countries as an emerging field of study". (64) investigated "CSR excites 'exponential' positive employee engagement: The Matthew effect in CSR and sustainable policy". After extensive review of literature we can conclude that CSR from employee's perspective and its impact on affective organizational commitment is not widely explored and there is significant research gap; therefore this study is aimed at exploring this gap. Furthermore, the study will investigate the moderating effect of emotional intelligence between relationship of corporate social responsibility and organizational commitment which is also not studied before.

MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY:

The methodology of this study is concerned in validating the research model by practicing appropriate methodology. Therefore, the rationale of this research methodology is clear and comprehensive about the study *i.e.* how the study is done and why thorough procedures are being utilized. The methodology has been developed on the basis of reviewing extensive literature review and the conceptual construct. Furthermore, the hypotheses have been developed based upon dependent and independent variables.

The current study is ascertained to the adoption of hypothetico-deductive method because the researcher has developed hypotheses based on extensive literature review. Cronbach's Alpha was analyzed on all the items of the research instrument. Then, AMOS 20.0 was used to generate the results and Structural equation modeling technique was tested to confirm the model fit of the study. Dependent and independent variables were used and analyzed through SPSS.

Independent Variable

The current study is conducted to examine the role of CSR on organizational commitment among frontline employees in different pharmaceutical companies. Therefore, the independent variable in this study is corporate social responsibility (Employee Perspective). Independent variable consists of 7 items measured on 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1 for strongly agree and 5 for strongly disagree).

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable in this study is increased organizational commitment. Dependent variable consists of 5 items measured on 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1 for strongly agree and 5 for strongly disagree).

Moderating Variable

In order to examine organizational CSR and its impact on organizational commitment EI is taken as moderating variable. Moderating variable consists of 5 items measured on 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1 for strongly agree and 5 for strongly disagree).

The quantitative study in this research is based on two major steps; pilot testing and the main study. Pilot testing was done at first so that the research instrument and the items adapted in this research process have an alliance with the problem of this study. First of all, validity was confirmed by having a brainstorming session with colleagues, mentoring personnel, and the respondents' views and it was initially confirmed that the items are fine enough to

provide coverage to the current issue. A total of 127 research questionnaires were administered to the target respondents who were at different positions working in pharmaceutical companies.

Hypothesis development and Conceptual framework

Following hypotheses were drawn from study:

H₁. Corporate social responsibility has a positive influence on organizational commitment.

H₂. Emotional Intelligence in collaboration with corporate social responsibility result in increased affective commitment

The below given figure # 1 is representing conceptual framework for this study

(Figure # 1)

RESULTS:

Studies suggest that the values of Skewness and Kurtosis should fall between -3 to +3. For this analysis, both in pilot testing and in main study the values of Skewness and Kurtosis fall between -3 to +3. This ensures the normal distribution of data. In

addition, descriptive statistics shows the mean values for EI, CSR, and OC. CSR has the highest mean *i.e.* 2.1818 whereas; EI has the lowest mean which is 2.0909 OC has a mean of 2.1387. The detail is shown in Table 1 given below.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
EI	127	1.22	3.78	2.0909	.55236	.545	.203	.189	.403
CSR	127	1.00	3.50	2.1818	.61286	.355	.203	-.693	.403
OC	127	1.17	4.00	2.1387	.69285	.573	.203	-.727	.403
Valid N (list wise)	127								

(where Inc. Hi is Increased Humanitarian Assistance)

Structural Equation Modeling and Co variance:

(Figure # 2)

Hypotheses	Estimate	S. E.	C. R.	P	Decision
H1 OC < --- CSR	0.743	.110	3.310	.000	Accept
H2 CSR < --- EI	0.687	.062	13.175	.000	Accept

AMOS 20.0 is used to produce the analysis of regression weights and generate structural equation model presented in Table 2 and Figure 2 above. The results indicate that if EI is increased by 1 CSR is also increase by 0.687 with standard error of .062 and critical ratio of 13.175. If CSR goes up by 1 increased OC also increases by 0.743 with standard error of .110 and critical ratio of 3.310. The value of P indicates the significance of the study which should

be less than 0.01. For H1, which states that CSR have a positive influence on OC; the value of P is acceptable at .000. Therefore, hypothesis H1 is accepted and same results were found by (Z. Prutina, 2016; Rhoades et al., 2001). For H2, this states that EI in collaboration with OC result in increased organizational Commitment of employees involved in supply chain, the value of P is also acceptable at .000. Therefore, hypothesis H2 is also accepted.

	Estimate	S. E.	C. R.
OC < --- CSR	0.346	.058	5.974 .000
CSR < --- EI	0.180	.040	4.534 .000

Table 3 indicates the co-variances among dependent and independent variables. The covariance between CSR and OC is estimated to be 0.346 and is significantly different from 0 at the 0.001 level (two-tailed), where the dependent variable is increased

organizational Commitment. The covariance between EI and CSR is estimated to be 0.180 and is significantly different from 0 at the 0.001 level (two-tailed); where the dependent variable is CSR.

CONCLUSION:

This study is an attempt by the researcher to throw light on effect of corporate social responsibility on affective commitment with moderating effect of emotional intelligence. The data was collected from employees of pharmaceutical companies. These employees always face issues of commitment as their work is most responsible in any organization. It is found by study that there is positive and significant effect of corporate social responsibility on organizational commitment and also emotional intelligence has positive effect as a moderator.

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